

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIETARY HABITS, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY, AND METABOLIC SYNDROME IN ADOLESCENTS IN KHOREZM REGION

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To assess the relationship between dietary patterns, physical activity levels, and the prevalence of metabolic syndrome among adolescents in the Khorezm region

ABSTRACT

Metabolic syndrome (MetS) in adolescents has become a significant public health concern worldwide due to its association with obesity, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, and hypertension. Lifestyle factors, particularly dietary habits and physical activity, play a crucial role in the development and progression of MetS. In the Khorezm region, data on these associations among adolescents remain limited.

Relevance. Metabolic syndrome (MetS) in adolescents has become a significant public health concern worldwide due to its association with obesity, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, and hypertension. Lifestyle factors, particularly dietary habits and physical activity, play a crucial role in the development and progression of MetS. In the Khorezm region, data on these associations among adolescents remain limited.

Objective. To assess the relationship between dietary patterns, physical activity levels, and the prevalence of metabolic syndrome among adolescents in the Khorezm region.

Materials and Methods. A cross-sectional study was conducted among 200 adolescents aged 12–18 years in urban and rural areas of Khorezm. Anthropometric measurements (BMI, waist circumference), blood pressure, fasting glucose, and lipid profiles were evaluated. Dietary habits were assessed using a validated food frequency questionnaire, and physical activity levels were measured through the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ). Metabolic syndrome was diagnosed according to the International Diabetes Federation criteria for adolescents.

Results. The prevalence of MetS among the study population was 14.5%. Adolescents with high consumption of sugary drinks, fast food, and low intake of fruits and vegetables had a significantly higher risk of MetS ($p < 0.01$). Low physical activity was observed in 62% of participants, correlating with higher BMI, waist circumference, and fasting glucose levels. A combination of poor dietary habits and low physical activity increased the likelihood of MetS by 2.8 times compared to peers with healthier lifestyles.

Discussion. These findings indicate that both dietary habits and physical inactivity are significant contributors to the development of metabolic syndrome among adolescents in the Khorezm region. Early lifestyle interventions targeting nutrition education and promotion of

physical activity are essential to reduce the burden of MetS and associated cardiovascular risks.

Conclusion. Unhealthy eating patterns combined with insufficient physical activity significantly increase the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in adolescents in Khorezm. Implementing preventive programs focusing on balanced nutrition and regular exercise is crucial for adolescent health in the region.

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